

Master thesis on Music and Sound Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Harmonic compatibility for loops in electronic music

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Co-Supervisors: António Ramires, Albin Correya, Frederic Font

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Abstract

In this work, we explore and compare a set of measures for harmonic compatibility. We focus our research on simultaneous harmonic compatibility for Loops in Electronic music. Loops are short and repetitive pieces of music meant to be played infinitely and are very popular in modern music production. The measures evaluated cover different algorithms and underlying mechanisms for harmonic compatibility. The mechanisms range from spectral matching and roughness to periodicity of the resulting signal. The measures are evaluated in an open experiment where participants are asked about their preference between pairwise comparisons of mixes suggested by the algorithms. We analyze the results with a statistical model that allows us to go from pairwise comparisons to a global ranking. We provide conclusions for this final global ranking, and also for our own observations of the suggested mixes. A complementary repository for this work is provided, containing the code, scripts, results, and links to the database of Loops.

With this work, we step towards a better understanding of the underlying mechanisms of harmonic compatibility. Also, the repository containing the code, allow future researchers to reproduce our work and explore the field of harmonic compatibility without having to implement the algorithms from scratch.

Keywords: Harmonic compatibility; Music creation; Consonance; Harmony

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context

In the beginnings of modern music production, the resources available for the music producers were very limited. The storage capability could not handle large amounts of audio collections ready for music creation. In the same way, the lack of means to share prevented the tools from spreading easily among users. However, the Internet made it possible to reuse audio excerpts and assets. Music producers found themselves from having a small number of resources made by themselves, to having a massive collection of audio fragments created by many different musicians. It is easy to handle a small well-known dataset, however, when the size increases and we can not see the whole picture at a glance the situation gets very complicated [1]. This causes users having to spend large amounts of time browsing through music resources until they find one that fits the piece of music they are working on.

1.2 Motivation

As technology was developed music also changed. This is not only related to the new instruments that were developed but also the way music is composed [2, 3]. Large-scale datasets of musical audio excerpts are not suitable for quick manual browsing. In-studio context, where time constraints are more relaxed, this is not a critical

problem, but with live music performances, time is crucial. Computer assistance using Music Information Retrieval (MIR) techniques could help musicians achieving better results in music live creation. However, no work puts all the State-of-the-Art Harmonic Compatibility algorithms in a common framework for comparison. This could be for several reasons: The lack of a database specifically designed for Harmonic Compatibility purposes difficult reproducibility and experimenting; Music is about culture and preferences [4], and therefore, about Harmonic Compatibility as well, making the evaluation harder.

Although Harmonic Compatibility is a concept that can be applied to every kind of music, the usefulness for this as an assistance tool is limited: Classical music is not done by overlapping existing sound fragments. For this reason, the work here will be based around Electronic Music, since in this music genre is very common reusing other audio excerpts to make music.

1.3 Objectives

1. Implement open-source versions of State-of-the-Art algorithms for harmonic compatibility. This will enhance the discussion and incite the MIR community to research and experiment more with harmonic compatibility.
2. Design an evaluation process that can be used for harmonic compatibility, with no ground-truth data.
3. Evaluate the advantages and drawbacks of each algorithm for harmonic compatibility, and find which algorithm is usually preferred by most people.

1.4 Structure of the Report

Besides this Introduction, this Master thesis dissertation contains 4 Chapters. In Chapter 2 the categories in which we can enclose the relevant algorithms are defined, along with the State-of-the-Art methods for each one. In Chapter 3 we describe the criteria to select the algorithms, the details for each one, and the database used

for harmonic compatibility. In Chapter 4 we expose the evaluation process for the generated audio samples, the results, and the statistical process used to analyze the results. Finally, in Chapter 5, we expose our conclusions and point new directions for research in harmonic compatibility.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Harmonic Compatibility is defined in many ways: Two musical excerpts that sound one after another can be more or less harmonically compatible, depending on how well they fit one after another. We can also refer to Harmonic Compatibility as the capability of two pieces of music to sound together and produce a pleasant sound. Those compatibilities are also usually described as *sequential compatibility* (Horizontal compatibility) and *simultaneous compatibility* (Vertical compatibility) [5]. In this work we will refer to the *vertical compatibility* when the *Harmonic Compatibility* expression appears, unless it's explicitly referred as *sequential compatibility*. The Harmonic Compatibility can be though in two different ways:

- Find a candidate audio with similar characteristics to the target audio. We will refer to this as: *Spectral similarity* measures
- Find a candidate audio such when mixed with the target audio, produces as much consonance as possible. Two sounds are said to be consonant if they *sound well together* or dissonant if they *sound poorly together* [5]. In some experiments when participants asked for the meaning of consonant they answered back with *beautiful* or *euphonious* [6]. We will refer to this as: *Dissonance/consonance* based measures.

The main difference between both approaches is that in the case of *Spectral simi-*

larity the results will try to find similar patterns in other audios. This means that if we want the most compatible audio excerpt for an *Augmented triad* the result will be close or exactly another *Augmented triad*. In the other hand, *Dissonance/consonance* approaches could come with different results because what it takes into account is *pleasantness*, *beauty* or *attractiveness* [7, 8] of the **resulting** sound. In this case, for an *Augmented triad* the most compatible result could be just a dyad containing the root and the octave. The second approach gives results based on the resulting consonance of the mix, while the first approach is more suitable to find mixes where the components have similar features.

2.1 Spectral similarity

Spectral similarity characteristics usually make use of higher-level representations of music. This can be chroma, pitch-spectrograms, and other similar features that generalize better the harmonic content of the sounds, rather than focus on isolated frequencies. Methods using spectral similarity range from simple correlation in the chroma domain [9], to intervals similarity adding aspects about dissonance [10].

2.1.1 Chroma matching

Chroma vectors are a way to condense tonal information of a musical fragment into their pitch classes ($C, C\#, D, D\#, E, F, F\#, G, G\#, A, A\#, B$). The use of *chroma* vectors in music has been widely explored and their uses range from chord recognition [11], to retrieving passages from classical music [12]. One of the use cases of chroma vectors which is more relevant to our research is the *AutoMashupper* [9]. The *Automashupper* algorithm aims to help users with mashups creation, a type of music made by blending two or more prerecorded songs. This blending can be performed by overlapping certain parts of the song, or by switching between sections of both tracks. The main problem to address for these music creations is to find song fragments that fit well when mixing. To solve this *Harmonic Compatibility* problem the authors use Chroma vectors synchronised with the beat of the songs.

By doing 2D convolutions between *Chroma* vectors of the songs, the authors are

able to find the beat and pitch offset that produces the biggest Harmonic Compatibility. This work also introduces a concept that doesn't exist in the other methods mentioned before in the SoA: Spectral Balance. To enforce the creation of spectral balanced mixes, the authors divide the spectrum into three different regions. By using the perceptual loudness for each of those three regions, and finding the beat offset that makes the spectrum the flattest possible we can define a spectral balance measure that depends on the beat offset between the audios. By summing both features (spectral and harmonic) the authors created a score for a given pair of songs:

$$M_n(k) = w_H M_{H,n}(k) \cdot w_L M_{L,n}(k)$$

Where $M_n(k)$ is the compatibility given beat offset k , $M_{H,n}(k)$ is the harmonic component of *mashability* for song n with beat offset k and $M_{L,n}(k)$ is the spectral balance component of the *mashability*. w_H and w_L are the weights for the harmonic and spectral components, being $w_H = 1$ for the harmonic component and $w_L = 0.2$ for the spectral component.

2.1.2 Tonal Interval Vectors

Approaches using raw *Chroma* does not take into account the aspects of human perception regarding intervals. In a *Chroma* vector, notes are arranged by their **closeness in frequency**, as opposed to models like the Tonnetz defined by Euler [13], that describe a space in which each pitch class is **closer** to other pitch classes which are **harmoniously more important** (see Figure 1). To address this lack of perceptual analysis of *Chroma* in Harmonic Compatibility models, the Tonal Interval Vector (TIV) feature is used in works as [10, 14, 15]. TIVs are defined in the following manner:

$$T(k) = w_a(k) \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \bar{c}(n) e^{-\frac{j2\pi kn}{N}}, 1 \leq k \leq 6 \in \mathbf{Z}$$

Figure 1: Tonnetz space. Source: Wikipedia

This expression will be explained in detail in section 3.1.1.2. The intuition behind this reformulation of the *Chroma* vector information is to get the most common intervals between pitch classes. Music theory has established since early studies that some intervals in the musical scale are more dissonant than others. By using the information of each interval presence and the dissonance that this arises in human listeners, TIV allows to predict how dissonant a sound will be. Using this model, the authors from [10] create a tool to find the sounds most similar to a certain one, prioritizing less dissonance in the resulting sound.

2.2 Dissonance/consonance based

Methods presented in this section are based on the dissonance/consonance created by different frequencies present in the spectrum when they sound together. This kind of approaches usually take symbolic representations in the form of sinusoidal models to represent a frame of the audio signal. For this section, we will follow the classification in [5] for the algorithms: Interference (and Interference subcategories), and Periodicity/Harmonicity (and its subcategories)

2.2.1 Interference: Pure dyads

Pure dyads consists on pairs of pure-tones sounding simultaneously. *Masking* and *beating* are both considered possible sources for pure-tone interference. However, ideas linking *masking* to consonance are quite sparse, and still need more empirical validation [5] in contrast to beating. Beating is the sensation arisen when two

Figure 2: Chroma vector and its TIV representation

frequencies very close in the spectrum, create a sensation of amplitude modulation. The resulting sensation produced by the beating between all the frequencies is called *Roughness*. This sensation is usually perceived as uncomfortable for most people.

There are several works aiming to build a model that recreates this perception of sound. The work done by Plomp & Levelt [6] was the basis for more accurate models. In their experiments, they asked participants to rate the consonance of different dyads. The parameters for each dyad were the geometrical mean of the tones and the difference between harmonics. Their findings were that roughness is primarily a function of the difference between frequencies of the dyads and the Critical Bandwidth (CB). CB is understood in this work as the range of frequencies on which two frequencies can not be heard as independent sounds. The total roughness for [6] is the sum of the roughness created by all adjacent frequencies. Instead of an algebraic model, their results are presented graphically on their work as in figure 3.

This idea of using CB as reference for roughness is also used in [16], but with a few

Figure 3: Roughness model presented in Plomp & Levelt[6]

differences. They use a different approach for the CB, with the expression:

$$CB = 1.72(\bar{f})^{0.65}$$

where \bar{f} is the geometric mean of the frequencies. The second difference is that instead of calculating the dissonances created by adjacent frequencies, it sums all the dissonances between all the differences in the spectrum. In their work [17], Gebhardt et al. propose a method to mix sound excerpts by trying to minimize the roughness of the result. The roughness model from Hutchinson & Knopoff [16] is used along with a *Pitch commonality* [18] model from Parncutt & Strasburger work. The authors extract 20 sines from each audio excerpt using the package *Spectral Modeling Synthesis Tools* [19], and then apply the roughness model to compute the overall roughness. In addition to this, to ensure the maximum Harmonic Compatibility between the two musical excerpts, the roughness is calculated through one octave divided into 97 pitch shifts (48 onward and 48 downward around a "no shift").

Another approach using *Interference* methods can be found in Maffei et al. [20]. Here the roughness calculation is the same as in the work of Gebhardt et al., however, instead of finding the pitch shift that minimizes the roughness, the authors try to attenuate the frequencies that contribute the most to dissonance.

2.2.2 Periodicity/Harmonicity

Theories based on Periodicity/Harmonicity predict consonance as result on the waveform's 'repetition' rate. Theories based on this have been explored with different approaches, including human voice periodicity as a way to predict consonance [21]. Periodicity can be calculated from the time or frequency representation of the sound:

1. Time: The waveform's repetitive structure.
2. Frequency: The capability of the spectrum of the sound to be expressed as integer multiples from a fundamental frequency.

However, mechanisms underlying *Periodicity/Harmonicity* theories are still subject of debate, being the most prominent theories for time based around *auto-correlation* of the waveform and for frequency around *pattern-matching*. However, in the list appearing in the annexes of [5], the most successful ones has been based around frequency.

2.2.2.1 Periodicity/Harmonicity: Spectral Pattern Matching

Spectral pattern matching states that listeners infer fundamental frequencies and pitch sensation from the pattern given by spectral peaks. This means that even when the fundamental frequency or some of its harmonics can not be heard, users can perceive the pitch sensation of the fundamental frequency. This pitch sensation is called *Virtual Pitch* (VP).

VP methods have been also explored for music creation purposes in Gebhardt et al. [17]. By calculating the pure tone height, masking, audible level and overtones for every pitch present in the sound, the authors of [18] create a model for VP. Gebhardt et al. takes advantage of this VP algorithm and calculate the three most prominent pitch sensations (resembling a triad) for the candidate and target song. Then *pitch commonality* is used to measure the consonance elicited by the 6 pitches. *Pitch commonality* algorithm from Hoffman-Engl work allows VP to classify chords

in Minor and Major keys [22]. This returns the strength of feeling for each of the 12 pitch classes, using a triad and all the combinations of three pitches in which overtones produce that same triad. This is done for the target and the candidate song, returning 2 series of 12 pitch sensations. The correlation of the two series is used then as a measure of consonance produced by the musical fragments.

However, the evidence in [17] shows that using pitch commonality along with roughness to measure Harmonic Compatibility results worse performance. This correlates with the results in Harrison & Pearce work [5], where Parncutt [18] is outperformed by other models that do not take into account masking, loudness, etc. In fact, the spectral pattern matching model with the best results according to Harrison & Pearce review of consonance models [5], only takes into account small deviation in the harmonics for the spectral pattern [23]. Instead of having just one fundamental frequency this method returns a probabilistic distribution and calculates the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence to this distribution from a uniform one. The intuition behind the KL divergence operation is that if the pitch sensations are not clear (no salient pitch), the KL divergence will be close to 0.

2.3 Evaluation in audio comparison

The lack of a ‘ground truth’ makes the Harmonic Compatibility task hard to evaluate, and also as mentioned before there is not much work done on Harmonic Compatibility. We can find an example of tests based on audio comparison in ABX tests, described in [24]. ABX test were designed for comparing two choices of audio stimuli to identify detectable differences between them. Users are presented with two reference sounds (A and B), and then with a third example (X) that must be identified as either A or B. The fact that this test does not use a scale rating make the test easy for the participants, resulting in less fatigue through different iterations of the experiment. However, this test is *forced choice* one, so even though participants can not distinguish any difference in the ABX stimuli they are forced to choose one, leading to frustration sometimes.

In *Automashupper* [9] for evaluating the quality of the results generated with their algorithm, the authors presented the participants with a target song, and then three different mixes for that song. The song used for each one of those mixes was: The one with the highest mashability score, the one with the score closest to the mean mashability score for that target song, and the one with the lowest mashability score. After listening the mixes participants were asked how much did they enjoyed the mix in a scale of zero to ten. Then this enjoyment mark can be used to find the correlation between the *Automashupper* mashability score and the rating given by the user, using the 3 mixes mentioned before. This process is repeated for different users and 10 different target songs. The authors also noticed that ‘the likelihood of very high harmonic similarity is much greater for a short section of 8 beats than one which is 64 beats containing multiple chord changes, hence it is not trivial to meaningfully relate *mashability* between phrase sections of different lengths’. For this reason the mixes were presented with a fixed length of 32 beats, a trade off between short 8 beats with high likelihood of harmonic similarity and a long piece of 64 beats that can make users feel tired during the experiments.

In their work for mixing based on roughness [17], Gebhardt & Davies instead of having just one rating as in [9] ask two different rankings to the participants: The *consonance* and the *pleasantness* of the mixes. Unlike *Automashupper* which looked for a musical excerpt in the library that returns high Harmonic Compatibility, the authors ‘force’ the mix between two musical excerpts and the variable is the pitch-shift returned by the algorithms of the study. Those algorithms are:

1. No shift;
2. Key Match. A tool from *Traktor DJ*¹ software;
3. The most dissonant according to roughness;
4. Consonant (Only roughness);
5. Consonant (Roughness + periodicity).

Figure 4: Ratings scores for experiments of Gebhardt & Davies. Source: [17]

Therefore, the final comparison is not between different rankings of the same algorithms, but the best results from different algorithms, allowing to find which one performs better through different examples.

2.4 Limitations of current work

Although the **consonance** problem has been widely studied, their application to music composition guidance and **Harmonic Compatibility** is barely explored. Most of the models are evaluated by ranking chords in terms of consonance/dissonance and then correlate the created ranking with human perception experiments [6, 5, 16]. Works like the one from Gebhardt et al. [17] or the Maffei’s experiments [20] allow us to confirm the usefulness of dissonance models for the task of making music mixes. However, pitch commonality based on [18, 22] is not the best algorithm for *spectral pattern matching* as demonstrated in Harrison & Pearce review of consonance models [5]. The experiments in Gebhardt et al. [17] can get the benefit of a finer *spectral pattern matching* algorithm like the one proposed in Harrison & Pearce work for harmonicity [23] instead of Parncutt & Strasburger [18], so we can explore better the contribution of *Periodicity/Harmonicity* to harmonic compatibility. Algorithms mentioned in section 2.1 are relatively new, and their evaluation barely comprehends comparison to other mashups/mix/dissonance models. All these reasons make it necessary to put all the algorithms into a common framework for music creation, to better define their drawbacks and advantages.

¹<https://www.native-instruments.com/en/products/traktor/dj-software/traktor-pro-3/>

Rankings based on scales as the ones proposed in [9, 17] are harder for users than choosing between pairs. Also, in the case of rankings based on score scales the ratings for the same mixes can be different between different users, even when preserving the same order of preference. ABX tests are very intuitive and quick to users, due to their pairwise comparison method. However, the fact that they don't allow for a 'no difference' option could result into an issue when trying to measure preference between different algorithms for Harmonic Compatibility. All these problems lead to design an evaluation similar to Urbano et al. work on crowd-sourced judgment for music similarity [25]. This kind of approach does not rely on scales but on preference between pairwise comparisons or given the case no preference.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, we will describe the methodology used to select the algorithms evaluated and how they were used to make the predictions for Harmonic Compatibility.

3.1 Algorithms

As described in Chapter 2, Harmonic Compatibility algorithms can be classified in two approaches: *Spectral similarity* and *consonance/dissonance*. We will discuss them in different subsections.

3.1.1 Spectral similarity

Most algorithms using spectral similarity and chroma matching are based on a 2D convolution of the *chroma vectors* of the song, combined with other methods, such as *spectral balance* and *rhythmic compatibility* from Automashupper [9], or *harmonic change rate* [26]. However, some of those aspects are not strictly related to vertical compatibility, which is the case of *harmonic change rate*. The latter one is based on how *chroma* vectors stay stable along with every beat of the audio excerpt. Audios can be classified as *totally unstable* or *totally stable*. This algorithm was presented by Lee et al. [26] and it tries to match together musical phrases that have a *high harmonic change rate*, with audios of *low harmonic change rate*. As the nature

of our research is to compare algorithms that work strictly vertically, we discarded such components to calculate Harmonic Compatibility. Aspects that were related to events happening concurrently, such as *spectral balance* (explained with more detail in section 3.1) were taken into account.

Tonal Interval Vectors bring a new perspective into *chroma vectors* based features. Moving the focus from pitch classes to interval distances allows taking into account the domain-knowledge of more and less dissonant intervals. Since the TIVs have been introduced recently, no variations or extra components were found in the current literature.

After taking into account these factors, we have the following algorithms for this section:

- Automashupper: Chroma convolution & spectral balance;
- Automashupper: Chroma convolution;
- Tonal Interval Vector: Framewise;
- Tonal Interval Vector: Beatwise;
- Tonal Interval Vector: Entire audio excerpt (Whole).

Notice that methods presented in this section will choose the original audio as the most compatible sound with itself. Throughout this section, when we mention *the most compatible audio*, we are referring to the audio that scored the 2nd higher value in the ranking.

3.1.1.1 Automashupper

Automashupper is one of the simplest approaches to this task. It uses the Chroma to calculate the Harmonic Compatibility between two musical excerpts that do not have to be exactly the same length. The authors from Automashupper presented two

versions for this algorithm. In the version from [27] which is the first one, the authors propose to calculate the cosine similarity between beat-synchronous Chromas.

$$H_n(r, k) = \frac{C_{i,p,r} \cdot C_{n,p,k}}{\|C_{i,p,r}\| \|C_{n,p,k}\|} \quad (3.1)$$

$H_n(r, k)$ is the *harmonic matching* value for given beat length k and pitch shift r . C refers to the *Chroma vector*, i to the input song, p the section of the song, and n to the candidate song. The pitch shift r is an integer in the range of ± 6 covering one octave, which is only applied in the input song. Notice that to create the mashup later, the r pitch shift is not applied to the original song, but $-r$ is applied to the candidate song n . A high harmonic similarity here will return a H_n value close to 1, whereas low harmonic similarity will return a H_n value close to 0. Using this measure is possible then to retrieve the most compatible music excerpts from a set of audios, in a normalized range.

However, the process as stated in [27] is slow and time-consuming. To solve this and other issues, a new Automashupper algorithm is presented by the same authors in [9]. In this second approach, although the idea behind *harmonic matching* still the same, the calculation is done differently. The authors stack vertically the *Chroma vectors* for every candidate song and then perform the 2D-Convolution between the *input chroma vector* and the *stacked candidate chroma vector*. To get the *Cosine similarity* we must divide the results of this 2D-Convolution by the denominator from Equation 3.1 and discard all the pitch-shifts out of the ± 6 range. The process is illustrated in Figure 5.

Taking only into account the *chroma vector* information can cause harmonically compatible but ‘unintelligible’ results. This is due to some excerpts that contain similar harmonic content and also similar spectral content. This overlap in frequency can cause masking between the melodies played by different instruments. To address this issue, the concept of *harmonic balance* of the resulting mix is introduced. Using the beat-locations and normalizing the audio with ReplayGain method [28], we retrieve the energy contained for 3 bands of the spectrum for every beat. The

Figure 5: 2D Chroma convolution. Input song in the front. Stacked chroma of the candidate audio in the background

regions are: low-band $f < 220Hz$, mid-band $220Hz < f < 1760Hz$, high-band $1760Hz < f$. We name this representation of the spectrum by L . After retrieving this information the mean is taken across the beat dimension for each band. The *spectral balance* is then calculated with a simple rule:

$$\beta_k = \frac{1}{K_p} \sum_{k=1}^{K_p} L_{i,p} + L_{n,k} \quad (3.2)$$

β_k is then normalised to the unit. Since we want a spectrum as flat as possible, spectral balance can be expressed as:

$$M_{L,n}(k) = 1 - std(\beta_k) \quad (3.3)$$

$M_{L,n}(k)$ will be closer to 1 when the spectral profile is flat, and 0 when its very uneven. Having those two scores we can finally have our measure of Harmonic

Compatibility:

$$M_n(k) = w_H M_{H,n}(k) + w_L M_{L,n}(k) \quad (3.4)$$

3.1.1.2 Tonal Interval Vector

As presented earlier, TIVs are defined in the following manner:

$$T(k) = w_a(k) \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \bar{c}(n) e^{-j\frac{2\pi kn}{N}}, 1 \leq k \leq 6 \in \mathbf{Z} \quad (3.5)$$

Where $\bar{c}(n)$ is a normalized version of the original chroma vector $c(n)$ divided by the DC component: $T(0) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} c(n)$. This normalization allow us to compare audios with different levels of energy but similar harmonic content [10]. The equation 3.5 resembles to a Fourier Transform applied to a Chroma vector. Following this process, we can calculate how frequent are the intervals contained in a Chroma vector, pondered with a set of weights $w_a(k)$. The weights provides domain knowledge about the dissonance that each interval k elicits. For our experiments we will use the weights proposed by Bernardes et al. [10]. According to the similarity with the Discrete Fourier Transform, we can define therefore [15]:

$$|T(k)| = \sqrt{\Re\{T(k)\}^2 + \Im\{T(k)\}^2} \quad (3.6)$$

$$\phi(k) = \tan^{-1} \frac{\Im\{T(k)\}}{\Re\{T(k)\}} \quad (3.7)$$

Where the norm of the vector represents which intervals are more present, and the phase represents where are those intervals located across the pitch classes. This means that to transpose the key of TIVs we only need to shift the phase. A pitch-

shifted version $T_p(k)$ of $T(k)$ by p semitones can be expressed as:

$$T_p(k) = |T(k)| \exp - \frac{j2\pi(k+p)}{N} \quad (3.8)$$

In the work of Bernardes et al. [10], the authors presented harmonic indicators based on TIVs:

1. **Dissonance:**

$$D = 1 - \frac{\|T(k)\|}{\|w_a(k)\|} \quad (3.9)$$

From the dissonance equation, we can therefore measure the dissonance between two overlapping tracks i, j :

$$D_{i,j} = 1 - \frac{\|a_i T_i(k) + a_j T_j(k)\|}{(a_i + a_j) \|w_a(k)\|} \quad (3.10)$$

Where $a_i + a_j = 1$. These weights allow to control the contribution of each song to the final mix.

2. **Perceptual relatedness:**

$$R_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^M |T_i(k) - T_j(k)|^2} \quad (3.11)$$

This is a measure of TIV similarity between two musical excerpts, regardless of the dissonance evoked by the resulting mix.

A *small-scale* measure between sounds i and j is provided in [10] given the previous dissonance and relatedness:

$$H_{i,j} = \bar{R}_{i,j} \bar{D}_{i,j} \quad (3.12)$$

Where $\bar{R}_{i,j} \bar{D}_{i,j}$ are the normalized version of $R_{i,j}$ and $D_{i,j}$. The small scale prioritize similar interval content (spectral similarity) but with a penalty for those mixes with

high dissonance. The lower is the H value, the more compatible are the two songs.

3.1.2 Consonance/Dissonance

Algorithms that try to measure or predict *consonance/dissonance* have been broadly studied, but for our work, those studies have a significant problem: Evaluation is done with isolated chords, pure tones, etc. The use of those algorithms to measure consonance in complex audio examples or non-symbolic music is barely explored. Given the number of works for *consonance/dissonance* in comparison with spectral similarity, we used the methods that provided the best results in Harrison & Pearce’s work on evaluating simultaneous consonance [5].

In the work of Harrison & Pearce [5], the authors compared how accurate consonance was predicted by different algorithms across several datasets. Those datasets were composed of chords and their consonance in a scale according to participants judgement. The correlation of the best performing algorithms is shown in *Figure A*, in the annex of [5], for comparison purposes. The two algorithms that performed better are the models from Hutchinson & Knopoff [16] for *interference between dyads* and Harrison & Pearce model for *harmonicity/periodicity* [23]. A model similar to Hutchinson & Knopoff has also been used for purposes similar to ours in the work from Gebhardt et al. [17]. The main difference is that the critical bandwidth (CBW) is now calculated with the approximation from [29] due to the arbitrary way in which the authors from [16] estimated CBW. Gebhardt et al. also use an *harmonicity/periodicity* model [18, 22] along with *dyads interference*. However, in their experiments, they found that this resulted in worse performance, so we will not add this second algorithm to our experiments.

Essentia library [30] also has algorithms for calculating *periodicity/harmonicity* and *interference between dyads*. The Essentia’s method *Inharmonicity* is used as a *Periodicity/Harmonicity* measure in the *vertical consonance* work of Harrison & Pearce [23], but it stands as one of the worst algorithms for predicting consonance in their ranking. The Essentia’s algorithm for *dyads interference* is called *Dissonance*, and is the model proposed in Plomp & Levelt [6], which served as a basis for the work

of Hutchinson & Knopoff [16]. We will add those algorithms to our selection to compare how the Essentia library could be used in its actual state for Harmonic Compatibility.

The models for this subsection uses pure tones as inputs, which can not describe effectively an entire bar or a beat of a musical excerpt. For this reason, all the algorithms in this *Consonance/Dissonance* section are calculated on a per-frame basis. For *consonance/dissonance* we have the following models:

- Gebhardt et al. roughness model (interference);
- Hutchinson & Knopoff (interference);
- Harrison & Pierce (periodicity);
- Essentia’s dissonance/ Plomp & Levelt (interference);
- Essentia’s inharmonicity (periodicity).

3.1.3 Consonance based: Roughness

All the *roughness* models presented here are based around the model from Plompt & Levelt. For this reason, we will expose the models chronologically, since some parts from earlier models will be the same for later versions. For each method we calculate the compatibility for all possible 12 pitches, except in the case of Gebhardt et al. In this last case, we divide every semitone into 8 parts, making a total of 96 possible pitch-shifts around a no-shift option. All the pitch-shifts were done using *PyRubberband*¹, a Python binding for the *Rubberband*² program for audio manipulation.

3.1.3.1 Plompt & Levelt

In their work *Tonal Consonance and Critical Bandwidth* [6], the authors explored the relationship between the *beating* effect arisen by two pure tones close in frequency,

¹<https://github.com/bmcfee/pyrubberband>

²<https://rubberbandaudio.com/?origin=breakfastquay>

and the frequency of those pure tones. For this purpose, they carried out one experiment where the listeners were asked to judge pure tone pairs on a scale of [1, 7]. In this scale 1 is the most dissonant sound and 7 is the most consonant one. When any subject asked for the meaning of *consonant*, they were answered with synonyms as *beautiful* and *euphonious*. Two main parameters were used to select the tone pairs to be presented to the subjects: geometric center of the pure tone pairs, and the frequency range of the pure tones.

The center frequencies used were: 125, 250, 500, 1000, and 2000Hz. Each of the subjects listened to 5 series of 12-14 tones. It is not mentioned here if the subjects had any musical training. The authors also discarded data from subjects whose responses were not consistent across the series.

Using results from this experiment the authors described consonance as a function of the difference between frequencies and the CBW of the geometric mean of the two frequencies. The relation is presented in graphically (see Figure 3) and no algebraic description is provided. To apply this to a series of tones the authors add the dissonance arisen by adjacent tones. This means that if we have 3 pure tones: f_1, f_2, f_3 the interaction between f_1, f_2 and f_2, f_3 will be taken into account, but the dissonance elicited by f_1, f_3 no.

The critical bandwidth was calculated according to the curve from Figure 6.

This method is implemented in Essentia as *Dissonance*³

3.1.3.2 Hutchinson & Knopoff

In their work Hutchinson & Knopoff [16] revisited the work, from Plompt & Levelt to study the relation between dissonance and Western musical theory. However, they made a few changes to the original approach.

Instead of using only adjacent tones, all the combinations of two tones of the set are taken into account. This means that in our previous comparison of three tones f_1, f_2, f_3 , the combination f_1, f_3 is not excluded for this occasion. The second

³https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_Dissonance.html

Figure 6: Critical bandwidth and frequency relation (solid line). Source: [6]

aspect is that the amplitudes of the tones are also used to calculate the final dissonance. The relation is given by the formula:

$$D = \frac{A_1 A_2 g(f_1, f_2)}{N} \quad (3.13)$$

Where A_1, A_2 are the amplitudes of the first and second pure tone, $g(f_1, f_2)$ is a function of the dissonance according to the involved frequencies, and $N = A_1^2 + A_2^2$ as the denominator. The g function is the one described in the Figure 3.

The last aspect which is modified is the estimation of the CBW. The authors argue that Plompt & Levelt critical bandwidth calculation is relatively ambiguous for two lowed-pitched sounds. As a solution they replaced this estimation with:

$$CBW = 1.72(\bar{f})^{0.65} \quad (3.14)$$

Figure 7: Comparison of critical bandwidth estimation as a function of frequency. The line labeled PL is the approach of [6] and the other one is the used in [16]. Source: [16]

Where $\bar{f} = \frac{f_1+f_2}{2}$. So for N pure tones, we measure the overall dissonance as:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N A_i A_j g_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i^2} \quad (3.15)$$

3.1.3.3 Gebhardt et al. model

This model is the first approach that aims to use dissonance as a measure to assist music mixing. Here an algebraic model of Figure [6] is taken from [31]:

$$g(y) = \begin{cases} (e^{\frac{y}{0.25}} e^{\frac{-y}{0.25}})^2 & y < 1.2 \\ 0 & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (3.16)$$

The final dissonance is expressed here in a way that the number of operations required is less than in equation 3.15:

$$D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1+i}^N A_i A_j g_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i^2} \quad (3.17)$$

However, one of the critical aspects that makes this different from the approach of Hutchinson & Knopoff, is the election of the CBW. In [16] the authors state: “we have arbitrarily extended their mean of CBW to low frequencies in a plausible way”. This election of the CBW is a subject of debate, and for this reason the calculation in Gebhardt et al. is done with the Equivalent Rectangular Bandwidth (ERB) formulae from [29]:

$$ERB(f) = 6.23(10^{-3}f)^2 + 93.39(10^{-3}f) + 28.52 \quad (3.18)$$

3.1.4 Consonance based: Harmonicity/Periodicity

Here we will explain the two selected methods based on *Harmonicity/periodicity*. There are no shared concepts between those algorithms, so the order of presentation is chosen based on the simplicity of the algorithm.

3.1.4.1 Essentia Inharmonicity

The Essentia *Inharmonicity* algorithm⁴ is an algorithm based on the energy contained in the harmonics of a series. To calculate the harmonic series we use two algorithms in Essentia: *HarmonicPeaks*⁵ and *PitchYin*⁶. This last one comes from the algorithm developed in [32], and calculates the pitch along with the confidence for the measure. For our experiments, we use the calculated pitch as a fundamental frequency regardless of the confidence coefficient of *PitchYin*. Using the *HarmonicPeaks* with the pitch from *PitchYin* we can feed the harmonic peak series into the *Inharmonicity* measure. In this last algorithm “the inharmonicity value is computed as an energy weighted divergence of the spectral components from their closest multiple of the fundamental frequency” [30]. The fundamental frequency is taken as the first frequency given in the series, and the output value can be 0 (completely harmonic) or 1 (completely inharmonic).

3.1.4.2 Harrison & Pearce Harmonicity

Harrison & Pearce, the authors from [5], also proposed a method to measure harmonicity/periodicity in [23]. By using pitch-class spectra they develop a method to calculate the salience of different pitch classes. This algorithm has some noticeable differences with the Essentia’s Inharmonicity one. The latter works directly on frequency, while this works on pitch classes. However, the most noticeable difference is that the Essentia’s Inharmonicity can only support one pitch class as salient while this one allows for different pitch classes to be salient.

Pitch-class spectrum is a representation based on the *perceptual weight* as function of pitch class p_c . This can be interpreted as how present is a given pitch class. Notice that this pitch-class spectrum is **continuous**, and pitch classes take values in the

⁴https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/std_Inharmonicity.html

⁵https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/std_HarmonicPeaks.html

⁶https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/std_PitchYin.html

range $[0, 12)$. The relation between frequency (in Hertz) f and p_c is given by:

$$p_c = \left[9 + 12 \cdot \log_2\left(\frac{f}{440}\right) \right] \text{mod } 12 \quad (3.19)$$

To allow harmonics to contribute to the pitch class of the fundamental frequency (despite not belonging that harmonic to the same pitch class), each pitch class is expanded into their implied harmonics. As stated by from [23] pitch-classes are modeled as harmonic complex tones with 12 harmonics, with decreasing intensity levels. This is accomplished using the *roll-off* parameter ρ with ($\rho > 0$), so the level of the j th harmonic is $j^{-\rho}$. $W(p_c, X)$ is the pitch class spectrum, for every pitch-class p_c and a given set of pitch classes $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$.

$$W(p_c, X) = \sum_{i=1}^m T(p_c, x_i) \quad (3.20)$$

i indexes the pitch classes from X , and $T(p_c, x)$ is the contribution of a harmonic complex tone with pitch class x to the pitch class p_c . This contribution can be calculated with the following expression:

$$T(p_c, x) = \sum_{j=1}^{12} g(p_c, j^{-\rho}, h(x, j)) \quad (3.21)$$

As we mentioned before pitch-classes are modelled as complex tones with 12 harmonics, which can be seen in the $\sum_{j=1}^{12}$ operation. $g(p_c, l, p_x)$ is the contribution of the harmonic with level l and pitch-class p_x to the pitch-class p_c .

$$g(p_c, l, p_x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2} \left(\frac{d(p_c, p_x)}{\sigma}\right)^2\right) \quad (3.22)$$

Notice that the expression in 3.22 allows certain deviation to the contribution controlled by σ and we can see the effects of this in Figure 8. $d(p_c, p_x)$ is the distance

Figure 8: Pitch class spectrum given $X = \{2, 3, 4\}$

between two pitch classes and it can be calculated as stated in equation 3.24.

$$d(p_c, p_x) = \min(|p_x - p_y|, 12 - |p_x - p_y|) \quad (3.23)$$

So far what we have accomplished is to calculate a pitch-class spectrum, but we need to use it for an *harmonicity/periodicity* measure. Let us define the *spectral distance* between two pitch sets X, Y as stated in [33]:

$$D(X, Y) = 1 - \frac{\int_0^{12} W(z, X)W(z, Y)dz}{\sqrt{\int_0^{12} W(z, X)^2 dz} \sqrt{\int_0^{12} W(z, Y)^2 dz}} \quad (3.24)$$

0 means maximum similarity while 1 means maximum dissimilarity. The virtual pitch-class spectrum Q defines the spectral similarity of pitch-class set X to an

harmonic complex tone with pitch class p_c :

$$Q(p_c, X) = D(p_c, X) \quad (3.25)$$

Where D is the spectral distance from Equation 3.24. This can be normalised to unit mass with:

$$Q'(p_c, X) = \frac{Q(p_c, X)}{\int_0^{12} Q(y, X) dy} \quad (3.26)$$

Q' allows interpreting Q as a probability distribution to hear certain pitch-classes. Finally, we measure harmonicity as the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence from an uniform distribution:

$$H(X) = \int_0^{12} Q'(y, X) \log_2(12 Q'(y, X)) dy \quad (3.27)$$

By using KL divergence we can take into account the salience of different virtual pitches. In a very *harmonic/periodic* sound, there will be clear peaks in virtual pitches Q , giving a KL divergence of 1. In the case of not very clear virtual pitch salience Q , will be flat, thus giving a KL divergence of 0.

Notice that in equations 3.24 to 3.27 the calculations are done through integrals. To speed up the calculation Harrison & Pearce divide the range of the pitch-class spectrum $[0, 12)$ into 1200 equally distanced points in their R implementation⁷ ⁸. Given the large corpora of music we have to analyse and the framewise-nature of consonance based algorithms, we used the same approach in our Python implementation. For the parameters σ and ρ we set the same values as in [23] $\sigma = 0.0683$ and $\rho = 0.75$.

⁷<https://github.com/pmcharrison/har18>

⁸<https://github.com/pmcharrison/hrep>

Algorithm	Category	Time-resolution	Name
Plompt & Levelt	Consonance: Roughness	Frame-wise	e_dissonance
Hutchinson & Knopoff	Consonance: Roughness	Frame-wise	hutchinson
Gebhardt et al.	Consonance: Roughness	Frame-wise	roman_diss
Inharmonicity	Consonance: Harmonicity	Frame-wise	inharmonicity
Harrison & Pearce Harmonicity	Consonance: Harmonicity	Frame-wise	p_harmon
AutoMashupper	Spectral similarity	Beat-wise	mashability
AutoMashupper no spectral balance	Spectral similarity	Beat-wise	mash_onlyh
TIV	Spectral similarity	Frame-wise	tiv_frame-wise
TIV	Spectral similarity	Beat-wise	tiv_beat-wise
TIV	Spectral similarity	Whole	tiv_whole

Table 1: Table with the algorithms, along with category, time-resolution, and implementation name

3.2 Dataset

The dataset we took is constructed from audios in the *Looperman* website⁹. This website is open for users (regardless they are professionals or not) to submit their music since 2006. It allows us to search by BPM range, user, title, genre, and category.

3.2.1 Selection of fragments

There are more than 100.000 examples available in *Looperman* only for the ‘loops’ section. We must keep the dataset used for the experiments in a reasonable size to ensure variety but also small enough so score computations can be calculated quickly. We discarded loops from the *percussion* category, given that we are addressing Harmonic Compatibility. We strictly focus on vertical consonance and not other issues related to mixing sounds with different lengths and therefore, we selected the loops with the most common BPM (140bpm). In addition to this, we divided this selection of loops into those with the same number of bars and selected the group with more examples inside (8 bars).

⁹<https://www.looperman.com/>

3.2.2 Trimming and refinement

As mentioned at the beginning of the section non-professional users can also upload their sounds to this platform, which sometimes can lead to poor trimming. This means that two audios with the same bpm, the same number of bars, and the same sample rate can have a different number of samples due to poor work when exporting the audio. To solve this problem we use the *confidence measure* presented in Font et al. [34]. This measure allows given a bpm and certain audio to estimate the real start and end of an audio, and how confident we can be about that ‘automatic trimming’ in a range of [0,1]. We discarded every audio for which confidence was below 0,98 and saved the trimmed version for use in the experiments.

After the selection described in the previous subsections, we have a list of 682 audios for our experiments. Notice that we filtered percussion by using the ‘category’ section in the metadata of the website. Given that this is a non-professional annotation sometimes the users uploaded drum segments or similar out of the percussion ‘category’, meaning that there were some examples from the list of 682 that had a high percussion content. After the experiments, we manually erased those examples, and in the *.csv* file uploaded in the repository, the audios with percussion sounds are not present.

3.3 Repository

The code used for this work is available on *GitHub*¹⁰. This repository includes the code of the algorithms, several instructions on how to use it, and the scripts used to calculate Harmonic Compatibility. A *.csv* is also attached in the repository with all the loops used for this project along with metadata and the links for each one.

¹⁰https://github.com/migperfer/harmonic_compatibility

Chapter 4

Evaluation

4.1 Score/Compatibility calculation

In this section we will explain in more detail the process used to calculate the *Harmonic Compatibility* scores for each algorithm detailed in 3.1.

4.1.1 Chroma-based

Automashupper score is defined in 3.1 and the calculation of its components and time resolution is clearly stated in the original publication. However, we will take two approaches to this algorithm. The first one is the Automashupper with the same parameters as [9] but omitting the *Rhythmic Matching* ($w_H = 1, w_L = 0.2$), thus only using *Harmonic Matching* and *Spectral Balance*. And the second approach is the Automashupper without *Spectral Balance* ($w_H = 1, w_L = 0$). So we can measure how important can be the effect produced by *Spectral Balance* in *Harmonic Compatibility*. As we can see in Table 2, maximum score is achieved when target and candidate song are the same one and no pitch of beat offset is needed. Notice that for our case, since all the audio excerpts will have the same size in terms of beats, the beat offset will be always 0.

In the case of Tonal Interval Vectors as mentioned in section 3.1 there is no length specified for which the TIVs should be calculated, therefore, we will take three

filename	mashability	pitch offset	beat offset	h contr	r contr
song1	1.2	0	0	1	1
song2	1.0	-2	0	0.8	1
...

Table 2: Mashability score and details for symbolic song *song1*

approaches:

1. *Framewise*: A TIV is calculated for every frame of the target and the candidate song. We calculate the *small scale compatibility* score between the simultaneous frames of candidate and target song. The final score is the mean *small scale compatibility* across all frames. See figure 9.
2. *Beatwise*: Similar to *framewise* but now the time resolution is the beat. For every beat a *chroma vector* is extracted and transformed to TIV. The mean is taken across the *small scale compatibility* score given by beatwise-TIVs of target and candidate song.
3. *Whole*: A single TIV for an audio excerpt is taken and the *small-scale* measure score is calculated between the pairs TIVs of candidate and target song

4.1.2 Consonance-based

All the models within this category use symbolic sine peaks as inputs. We extracted these sines with the *sinusoidal model* presented in [35]. This represents a spectrum as a combination of sines from which we can reconstruct the original spectrum minimizing the mean squared error. As mentioned before, all the models in this category will be used in a *framewise* manner. The length of the window is 2048, the number of points for FFT is 2048, hop size 1024, and the number of sines per frame is 20. The mean values across all frames will be used as the final score for compatibility, similar to the framewise TIV, but with a small difference: We mix candidate and target loop, and we calculate use the frames for the mix and not for the separated tracks.

Figure 9: TIVs score when using TIVs in a Framewise/Beatwise manner

4.2 Overview of the first results

For all the 9 target audios we created the mixes that scored the 5 highest compatibility scores for each algorithm. After listening to all the generated samples we made a some observations for the algorithms.

In roughness based methods and specially Hutchinson & Knopoff [16] and Gebhardt [17] models, the trend is to find audio excerpts that are ‘distant’ or ‘not coincident’ in terms of frequency. This is related with the fact that those models find frequencies that create dissonance within the same critical bandwidth. In consequence, avoiding overlapping regions of the spectrum will result in a higher compatibility measure. This bias is not so noticeable in the Plompt & Levelt [6] model, since it only calculates dissonance between adjacent frequencies reducing the influence this can have. In Gebhardt et al., this effect has no relevance since the purpose of their work is finding the best pitch shift to blend two complete musical excerpts. However, in our case, the music excerpts are composed by a small amount of instruments which do not usually cover a big portion of the spectrum, introducing a noticeable bias in the

results.

In the case of both Automashupper versions we noticed a preference to score with high values candidates consisting in drum/percussion. This can be explained by the fact that percussive sounds have usually a more plain chroma vector. This results in higher values when performing the chroma convolution, thus achieving higher scores for the Automashupper.

Lastly, we observed that for the Harrison & Pearce model for *periodicity/harmonicity*, has a preference for FX effects consisting on noise-sweep sounds similar to the one in this example¹. A possible explanation for this is that noise-sweep FX sounds are located in a narrow band of the spectrum, contributing to a high pitch salience. However, this case is not found for the *periodicity/harmonicity* method based on Essentia *Inharmonicity* measure.

4.3 Online survey

The main goal of this project is to compare all algorithms and determine which one of them produce the best results for *Harmonic Compatibility*. However, as mentioned in the sections 2.3 and 2.4, all the approaches taken until the moment lack of a natural way to compare between different algorithms. For this reason we developed a method consisting on pairwise comparisons which will be later expanded to a global ranking.

4.3.1 Selection of target loops

As mentioned in the previous section, some algorithms have a bias due to the way energy is distributed across the spectrum of target and candidate. This could result in a specific algorithm that outperforms all others for a certain type of instrument. Due to this reason, we decided to diversify our selection of instruments keeping a wide range of instruments: Synth, vocal, acoustic, bass, growl bass, etc. Broadening our categories we can estimate which algorithms perform better in general. The

¹<https://freesound.org/people/Timbre/sounds/192430/>

final selection of loops is available in the GitHub repository, under the CSV folder.

4.3.2 Description of the survey

Giving a score to each mix in a predefined scale (for example $[0, 10]$) can be very unnatural for users and sometimes it can be time consuming, leading eventually to frustration and quitting the experiment. Also, it can happen that for the same series of examples, two users gives different scores to the series but keeping the order of preference. This reasons lead us to base our test in a similar manner to ABX tests described on section 2.3. However, instead of presenting 2 references (A, B) we present only one (Original song) which is the target audio. This target audio serves as reference for the two possible mixes (#1 and #2) presented. The users must choose which mix they prefer, or given the case, no preference. For the 10 algorithms we test, the amount of pairwise combinations without repetition is 45, being a total of 405 possible examples given our 9 different target loops.

The survey is hosted online² and open to everyone, so we can get several of comparisons between the algorithms. An example of the iterations can be seen in Figure 10. Participants can choose either mix #1, mix #2, or no preference. Users were asked to do this process 15 times. We choose this number of iterations because it is long enough so a single user ranks a sensible amount of pairwise comparison, but not long enough so participants feel exhausted and feel less predisposed to make some more classifications in the future.

4.3.3 Analysis of the pairwise comparisons

After collecting 551 comparisons from the survey users, we proceeded to the analysis of the model. To this goal we used the tools given in the PlackettLuce [36] model, that allows us to estimate a global ranking of the algorithms according to the intrinsic ‘worth’ of each one. PlackettLuce is based on Luce’s axiom choice [37] which states that the odds of choosing an item over another do not depend on the set of items from which the choice is made. For a given set of algorithms $S = \{i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_t\}$

²<https://web-survey-273418.appspot.com/>

Round: 1/15

Original song

#1

#2

Mix #1
 Mix #2
 No preference

Figure 10: Example of an iteration of the survey

we can assign to each one a certain ‘worth’. So the probability of choosing the algorithm j is:

$$P(j|S) = \frac{\alpha_j}{\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i} \quad (4.1)$$

Usually α_i is forced to be a positive number, and the ‘worths’ are restricted such as $\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i = 1$. We will use the implementation from [36] which return ranks of the form:

$$R = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots\} \quad (4.2)$$

Where elements in C_1 are ‘better’ or have more ‘worth’ than items in C_2 , and so on. If there are multiple elements in item C_j those elements are *tied* in that ranking.

For a set of items S we define the function:

$$f(S) = \delta_{|S|} \left(\prod_{i \in S} \alpha_i \right)^{\frac{1}{|S|}} \quad (4.3)$$

where $|S|$ is the cardinality of the set (the number of elements that the set has), δ_n is a parameter that relates to the prevalence of ties of order n . The authors from [36] define the probability of the ranking R that allows ties of order D as:

$$\prod_{j=1}^J \frac{f(C_j)}{\sum_{k=1}^{\min(D_j, D)} \sum_{S \in \binom{A_j}{k}} f(S)} \quad (4.4)$$

where D_j is the cardinality of A_j , the set of alternatives from which C_j is chosen, and $\binom{A_j}{k}$ are all the possible combinations of k elements from A_j without repetition and without order relevance. This D parameter can be set to the maximum number of allowed ties so $\delta_n = 0$ for $n > D$

Using log-likelihood we fit the results from our survey to the different R rankings proposed with probabilities given by equation 4.4.

4.3.4 Results

The results of the survey are available in the repository for this work under the *csv* folder. Each entry in the *.csv* is an iteration of the survey, and contains:

- *algo1*: The first algorithm presented in the comparison.
- *algo2*: The second algorithm presented in the comparison.
- *chosen_algo*: An integer with the chosen algorithm by the participant. 1 for *algo1*, 2 for *algo2* and 0 in case of tie.
- *target*: The name of the audio used as target.

	<i>estimated worth</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>quasiSE</i>	<i>quasiVar</i>
<i>e_dissonance</i>	0.000	0.000	0.229	0.052
<i>hutchinson</i>	0.799	0.312	0.2146	0.046
<i>inharmonicicity</i>	1.656	0.322	0.220	0.048
<i>mashability</i>	0.996	0.313	0.209	0.044
<i>mashability_onlyh</i>	0.467	0.311	0.217	0.047
<i>p_harmon</i>	0.263	0.312	0.218	0.047
<i>roman_diss</i>	0.505	0.311	0.214	0.046
<i>tiv_beatwise</i>	2.194	0.337	0.241	0.058
<i>tiv_framewise</i>	1.040	0.312	0.210	0.044
<i>tiv_whole</i>	1.739	0.324	0.222	0.049

Table 3: Estimate worth for each algorithm along the Standard Error, quasi Standard Error, and quasi Variance

- *global_number*: A number with which identifies a unique combination of *algo1*, *algo2* and *target*.
- *timestamp*: A timestamp of when that iteration's result was stored.

After fitting our results using the *R* *PlackettLuce*[36] package we obtained the worth of each algorithm, along with the standard error, quasi standard error and quasi variance. This is presented in Table 3.

Figure 11: Worth for each algorithm along with their standard errors

Chapter 5

Conclusions and future work

In this chapter, we will discuss our observations of the generated examples and the survey responses. Under those results, we will propose new approaches for this task.

5.1 Conclusions

The results in Table 3 indicate that Tonal Interval Vectors in a beatwise manner have a higher chance of being selected by the users when presented with any of the other algorithms. The inharmonicity method from Essentia and TIV whole, appear with similar worths directly after TIV beatwise. In the section with worths closer to the mean worth value, we can see TIV framewise, mashability, and Hutchinson. In the last zone of the plot, *p_harmon*, mashability without spectral balance, Gebhardt's dissonance, and Essentia dissonance appears as those with less preference.

TIV beatwise is the most preferred method for harmonic compatibility. This reflects that harmonic matching itself is not sufficient for harmonic compatibility, but also the dissonance arisen by the different intervals contained. TIVs seems to improve their results with a balance in the time resolution. This could be explained because framewise TIVs allow less flexibility in the harmonic content within a bar, discarding loops that although dissonant sometimes still valid for human perception within an appropriate time range. In this sense, TIV whole with a poor time resolution

allows very unpleasant dissonances prolonged in time. Also, TIV whole could vary the result given here depending on the size of the audio excerpts considered. For audios larger than 32 beats (our case), the outcomes could get even worse than the framewise approach.

Nevertheless, even TIV framewise matches the worth for Mashability. This leads to the conclusion that besides the importance *chroma vector* matching, the dissonance arose by the blend of the mixes plays a sensible role for harmonic compatibility. Mashability that does not take into account spectral balance has a slightly worse result than the full Mashability described in section 3.1. This means that although spectral balance is relevant for harmonic compatibility, it does not play a key role.

Models based on roughness occupy a low tier on the preference scale, with only the model based on Hutchinson & Knopoff’s work having a nice degree of acceptance. However, as mentioned before in Section 4.2, for our task these models have a bias due to their nature that benefits ‘distant’ spectral content rather than similar harmonic content. The results might be different for algorithms in this category if the task were done with full tracks rather than isolated instruments.

Essentia’s Inharmonicity have also a reasonable high worth. This is not surprising since the patterns in which pitches are organised reflect a periodic order that has a higher score for this algorithm. *Essentia’s Inharmonicity* algorithm having better results than a complex algorithm as *p_harmon* can surprise, but this could have a simple explanation. While *p_harmon* allows for multiple pitch salience and flexibility, *Essentia’s Inharmonicity* **requires** the final mix to have a very clear and salient pitch with their series of harmonics. Meaning that although some flexibility in pitch salience is allowed, a more clear and salient pitch sound will be preferred by most people. It is important to notice that for *p_harmon* we followed the same approach as Harrison & Pearce, meaning that we do not take into account the amplitude of the extracted frequencies in contrast to *Essentia’s Inharmonicity*.

5.2 Future work

The results and discussion presented in the previous section arise for new questions. Harrison & Pearce [5] present a composed model based on *Roughness*, *Periodicity/Harmonicity* and *Culture*. Similarly, a way to improve the results of the actual SoA for this task could be achieved by using a blend of TIV Beatwise, *Essentia's* Inharmonicity, and spectral balance. This process should take into account different weights for each algorithm, so we can explore not only how to combine them to have a better *Harmonic Compatibility* algorithm, but also investigate preference of the underlying mechanisms for different users. Also, the number of sines that gives in general better results with *Essentia's* *Inharmonicity* should be explored, since it is almost matching the most preferred algorithm.

All the methods proposed here use domain knowledge, still, deep learning approaches have been proved to outperform hand-tailored algorithms by experts in Music Information Retrieval, like Tempo estimation [38]. Using a database of tracks stems as MedleyDB [39], along with triplet ranking loss could embed audios into a space where harmonically compatible sounds are close.

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